

A psychosocial perspective on childhood cancer: understanding and addressing the needs of patients and their families

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Preface and acknowledgments

While the purpose of submitting this dissertation is to fulfill the criteria for obtaining a doctoral degree, I would like to emphasize that its significance does not lie in personal accomplishments, but in its content. Childhood cancer has a profound impact on the lives of children and their families, and I sincerely hope that my research will help to improve their well-being. I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to all the patients and families who took the time to participate in the underlying studies and share their personal experiences with me. I am convinced that their stories will contribute to the current state of research and the future experiences of other affected families in a very positive way.

This work focuses on children and families who may severely suffer physically and emotionally, but ultimately survive the disease. I am humbled by the fact that I live in a part of the world where most children with cancer do. However, it is important to me to mention the many families who lose their child to cancer and the families who live in parts of the world where access to high-quality healthcare is not as self-evident as it is here. In 2018, the World Health Organization launched the Global Initiative for Childhood Cancer, which aims to significantly improve survival rates on a global scale by 2030.¹ I hope that one day, all children with cancer can be promised a cure, and that the field of psychosocial oncology and survivorship will become a priority for all, making this area of research and care all the more important.

I would like to express my gratitude to the University of Lucerne and its Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, as well as to Prof. Gisela Michel, for giving me the opportunity to work as a research assistant on the GROKkids project and to complete my dissertation within this project.

Prof. Michel's supervision provided me with invaluable learning experiences and constant support that was not limited to academic matters. Through her mentorship, I not only gained knowledge and skills, but also built confidence in my abilities, a foundation that I believe will serve me well

throughout my entire professional journey. I am very grateful for her unwavering commitment and investment in my PhD and the numerous interesting and enjoyable discussions we had.

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Although I had a certain amount of freedom in choosing the research questions and methods for the underlying papers, it is important to emphasize that I certainly did not work alone, even though I am writing this dissertation from a first-person perspective. In all my work, I could rely on the valuable support of my co-authors, especially my supervisors, namely Prof. Gisela Michel, Dr. Daniela Dyntar, Dr. Peter Francis Raguindin, Prof. Fiona Schulte, and Dr. Vicky Lehmann.

I am especially grateful to Dr. Daniela Dyntar, who taught me that a PhD is about the person I want to become, not the certificate I want to get. Her passing is deeply mourned. I would like to extend my gratitude to the entire team led by Prof. Gisela Michel for the enriching experiences, both professionally and personally. I am deeply grateful for the many friendships that have grown out of our work together.

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I would like to thank my family and my partner for their unwavering support throughout, especially for always encouraging me to follow my own path, even if this meant being far away from them.

Abstract

Background. This dissertation aimed to understand and address the psychosocial challenges faced by childhood cancer patients and their families during treatment and beyond. More specifically, the aims were to: 1) explore the psychosocial experiences of grandparents during the acute phase of their grandchild's cancer treatment, 2) examine the prevalence and associated factors of fertility-related concerns in long-term childhood cancer survivors, and 3) provide practical guidance on screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship.

Methods. Semi-structured interviews were used to explore the psychosocial experiences of grandparents during their grandchild's cancer treatment, as this has been an area with limited previous research findings. In addition, a quantitative cohort study was conducted to gather generalizable data on fertility-related concerns among childhood cancer survivors, complementing previous qualitative studies. Furthermore, a systematic literature review synthesized existing evidence relevant to mental health screening in follow-up care.

Results. The challenges experienced by grandparents during their grandchild's cancer treatment were notable, yet many demonstrated coping strategies and reported positive outcomes despite these adversities. Long-term survivors of childhood cancer frequently expressed fertility-related concerns, especially when looking at longitudinal patterns, highlighting the significance and persistence of such concerns. There are numerous options for implementing brief mental health screening tools in survivorship care that can be delivered by professionals from multiple disciplines after appropriate training.

Conclusion. Childhood cancer patients and their families face multiple psychosocial challenges that require attention in both the immediate and long-term contexts. Grandparents should be considered in the context of childhood cancer. Psychosocial follow-up care for survivors should include the exploration of fertility-related concerns and early identification of general mental health problems through systematic screening.

List of abbreviations

APA	American Psychological Association
AYA	Adolescent and young adult
BSI-18	Brief Symptom Inventory-18
CCS	Childhood cancer survivors
CNS	Central nervous system
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease of 2019
DT	Distress Thermometer
ICCC-3	International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition
LTFU	Long-term follow-up
N/A	Not applicable
N/S	Not specified
Peds-QL	Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PROSPERO	Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews
PSCPCC	Psychosocial Standards of Care Project for Childhood Cancer
REC	Recommendation
SCL-90	Symptom Checklist-90
SDI	Sociodemographic index

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1. INTRODUCTION AND MAIN OBJECTIVE

Childhood cancer is a complex challenge in pediatrics, posing a threat to the health and well-being of children worldwide. Despite its low incidence, there are thousands of new cases each year,² making childhood cancer a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide.³

To date, there are large regional variances in diagnosis, treatment, and survival rates.⁴ In countries with a high sociodemographic index (SDI; a comprehensive indicator of development status that is strongly correlated with health outcomes⁵), almost all children with cancer are properly diagnosed and receive high-quality treatment,² resulting in most of them surviving the disease.⁶ Unfortunately, this is not the case in countries with a low SDI, where about half of children with cancer remain undiagnosed,^{2,7} and survival rates are as low as 30%.⁸ While the focus in low-SDI regions remains on improving access to diagnosis and treatment and ultimately improving survival,¹ the focus in countries with a high SDI has shifted to advancing practice, science, delivery, implementation, and standardization of supportive care;⁹ a holistic approach to care that addresses symptoms and treatment side effects and provides physical, psychological, social, and spiritual support from diagnosis through end-of-life care.¹⁰ Given that the research underlying this dissertation was conducted in or related to high-SDI countries, the focus will be on these healthcare settings. Furthermore, the focus will be on the children who survive and not on the families who lose their child to cancer.

In addition to physical challenges,^{3,6} childhood cancer can have a profound impact on the psychosocial well-being of both children and their families.¹¹ Despite the increased burden during diagnosis and treatment, which elicits a range of emotions including fear, anxiety, sadness, and uncertainty, the impact extends well into survivorship.¹² Childhood cancer survivors are at increased risk for psychosocial late effects, which may or may not be associated with physical late effects.¹¹ It is critical to thoroughly understand and address these psychosocial experiences and to provide patients/survivors and their families with support and resources to help them cope with the psychological challenges they face. *Therefore, the overall objective of this dissertation was to understand and address the psychosocial challenges faced by childhood cancer patients and their families throughout the cancer continuum.*

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. An introduction to childhood cancer

Cancer is a term used to describe a group of diseases characterized by an uncontrolled division of abnormal cells that can spread to other parts of the body through the blood and lymph systems.¹³ These cells can form tumors, i.e., lumps of tissue.¹⁴ *Childhood cancer* includes a variety of tumors and is characterized by the age of the affected individual and not by specific disease characteristics, such as the tumor location,¹⁵ as it is usually the case with adult tumors (e.g., breast cancer). Childhood cancer is rare and accounts for only about 4% of all cancer diagnoses.¹⁶ Nevertheless, there are about 400,000 new cases of childhood cancer worldwide each year.² The World Health Organization (WHO) considers the diagnostic age range for childhood cancer to be 0-19 years.¹⁵

Unlike many adult cancers, childhood cancers do usually not have an external cause, such as environmental and/or lifestyle factors,¹⁵ except for prior high-dose radiation and chemotherapy.¹⁷ On the other hand, congenital risk factors (e.g., higher birth weight, advanced parental age, birth defects) and genetic variations are proven to be associated with childhood cancer.¹⁷ Childhood cancer is not considered preventable, but can be detected in its early stages,¹⁸ which is particularly important because childhood cancer tends to progress quickly and is very aggressive.¹⁹ In Western Europe and North America, diagnostic practices are very good, with only 3% of children remaining undiagnosed.² The standard classification of childhood cancers is provided by the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition (ICCC-3),²⁰ which divides them into 12 main diagnostic groups:

- I. Leukemias, myeloproliferative diseases, and myelodysplastic diseases
- II. Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms
- III. Central nervous system (CNS) and miscellaneous intracranial and intraspinal neoplasms
- IV. Neuroblastoma and other peripheral nervous cell tumors
- V. Retinoblastoma
- VI. Renal tumors
- VII. Hepatic tumors

- VIII. Malignant bone tumors
- IX. Soft tissue and other extraosseous sarcomas
- X. Germ cell tumors, trophoblastic tumors, and neoplasms of gonads
- XI. Other malignant epithelial neoplasms and malignant melanomas
- XII. Other and unspecified malignant neoplasms

In younger childhood cancer patients (0-14), the most common diagnoses are leukemias (an uncontrolled increase of white blood cells in the bone marrow¹⁸), CNS tumors (masses in the brain or spinal cord²¹), and lymphomas (cancer that affects the lymphatic system¹⁸).²² In adolescents (15-19), the most common diagnoses are lymphomas, as well as epithelial tumors (arise from/are composed of epithelial cells²³) and melanomas (begin in the melanocytes, i.e., the cells that produce the pigment melanin²³).²²

Cancer is generally harmful and can lead to death if left untreated.¹⁵ *Pediatric oncology* is the medical specialty that focuses on the treatment of childhood cancer.²⁴ Common *treatments* include surgery, chemotherapy, radiation therapy, immunotherapy, stem cell transplantation, or a combination of these.^{24,25} The appropriate treatment depends on the specific type of cancer, its stage of progression, and child characteristics.²⁴ The aim of surgery is to remove the tumor and its surrounding tissue.²⁶ Chemotherapy, usually administered in a certain number of cycles, uses drugs to destroy cancer cells and prevents them from dividing.²⁶ In radiation therapy, oncologists use high-energy beams or particles to destroy tumor cells.²⁶ Immunotherapy uses the patient's own immune system to fight the cancer cells (e.g., through cancer vaccines).²⁶ Stem cell transplants replace cancerous bone marrow with cells that will develop into healthy bone marrow.²⁶

Over the past decades, pediatric oncologists have joined together in large international and interdisciplinary study groups to continuously improve treatment.⁶ These improvements have led to tremendous increases in *survival* rates. While the survival rate was as low as 30% in the mid-20th century, it has now risen to over 80% in countries with a high SDI.⁶ These advances mean that most childhood cancer patients become *survivors* (≥ 2 years²⁷) or *long-term survivors* (≥ 5 years²⁸) today.

These survivors can be divided into three distinct age groups that correspond to their developmental stage (Figure 1).²⁹

FIGURE 1 Distinct age groups of childhood cancer survivors

Note: Adapted from Tutelman & Heathcote, 2020.²⁹

Even though they are highly efficient, modern cancer therapies are very aggressive and, therefore, require a careful trade-off between efficacy and toxicity.⁶ *Acute toxicities* are those that usually resolve after completion of treatment (e.g., hair loss or vomiting during chemotherapy).³⁰ More concerning, cancer therapies can cause *late effects* that persist until or occur long after treatment has ended.³⁰

Long-term survivors of childhood cancer have twice the burden of disease as the general population.³ A large cohort study from the United States showed that by the age of 45, more than 95% of survivors had at least one chronic health condition and 80% had at least one serious, disabling or life-threatening condition.³ These late effects are diverse in nature. In addition to an increased risk of *second primary malignancies*,³¹ late effects may occur in the cardiovascular, renal, hematologic, ocular, gastrointestinal, pulmonary, endocrine, musculoskeletal, reproductive, infectious, and auditory systems.³

To detect these late effects early and initiate timely interventions, *survivorship care* is highly recommended.³² Long-term follow-up (LTFU) care should be available to all childhood cancer

survivors (CCS) throughout their lives.³³ Today, survivorship care goes beyond medical aspects and includes psychological and/or social support (refer to chapters 2.2 and 2.5).¹⁰

2.2. An introduction to psychosocial oncology

Psycho-oncology has its roots in the mid-1970s, when it started to become a sub-specialty of oncology.³⁴ It is a field that addresses the psychological and emotional aspects of cancer, focusing on the well-being of patients by integrating mental health support into oncology care.³⁵ The initial conditions for the emergence of psycho-oncology stemmed from cultural changes, including the destigmatization of both cancer and mental health problems.³⁵ In addition, changes in the dynamics between healthcare providers and patients, a shift in focus from simply increasing survival to improving quality of life, and advances in palliative care all played critical roles.³⁵ Since its early days, the scope of psycho-oncology has continued to expand.³⁶

The term *psychosocial oncology* is an extension of psycho-oncology to social aspects³⁶ and is therefore used as the basis for this dissertation.

Psychosocial oncology [...] is the study of the interactions between psychological and social processes on one hand, and the development and progression of cancer and their psychosocial side effects on the other. It is concerned with evidence-based care, advice, and treatment of cancer patients of all ages and their relatives in the various phases of the disease, i.e., in acute care, aftercare, prevention and rehabilitation. The aims are to support patients in coming to terms with their illness, stabilizing their quality of life, social reintegration and, if applicable, improving their survival prognosis.

([translated from German to English]; Schwarz & Götze, 2008, p.223)³⁶

Even though some aspects of this generic definition are not applicable to childhood cancer (e.g., development and prevention of cancer), it is a good basis for a holistic understanding of psychosocial oncology. A schematic representation of the key aspects of the definition is shown in Figure 2. Psychosocial oncology is thus concerned with understanding the psychosocial experiences of patients and their families, as well as addressing them in clinical care. For an optimal outcome, it is

important that these areas influence each other, i.e., that research is conducted in order to sustainably improve practice and, conversely, that practice is evidence-based. Overall, psychosocial oncology involves the experiences of patients and their families throughout the whole cancer continuum, all the way from diagnosis to survivorship.

FIGURE 2 Schematic representation of the key aspects of psychosocial oncology

Note: Key aspects of psychosocial oncology as defined by Schwarz & Götze, 2008.³⁶

2.3. The acute psychosocial impact of cancer and its treatment

The time around diagnosis and during (early) treatment has been identified as particularly distressing for patients and their families.¹¹ During this time, the psychosocial adjustment of patients strongly depends on environmental factors, which is why it is so important to also consider family members and dynamics.^{11,37,38} A systematic review found a significant association between family functioning and child adjustment across studies.³⁹

Patients experience a variety of psychosocial outcomes.¹¹ Painful medical procedures and treatment-related side-effects are inevitable and can be experienced as highly threatening and aversive by children.³⁸ They can lead to severe anxiety, traumatization, pain intolerance, or even treatment

refusal.^{11,38} Overall, patients' experiences are highly dependent on their age. Infants, toddlers, and preschoolers have a limited understanding of the situation and may thus be better able to integrate cancer into their lived reality,⁴⁰ especially as they might not remember a 'time before cancer'. Older children, on the other hand, may have a more difficult time adjusting because of their wish to look and feel normal.⁴⁰ They report wondering why they got sick, feeling isolated and sad, or not being able to play as they want.⁴¹ On the other hand, they have a better understanding of why treatment is important and will help them in the long run.¹¹ It is important to note that symptoms may present differently in children than in adults. Anxiety, for example, may present as irritability, physical restlessness, or an increase in somatic complaints.¹¹

For *parents*, the cancer diagnosis of their child is devastating. Previous research shows that although they were concerned about their child's symptoms, they would have never expected it to be cancer.⁴² Across studies, parents of children undergoing treatment face a wide range of challenges, including administrative and financial strain, disruption of daily routines, communication problems, and increased levels of mental health problems, such as depression and anxiety.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ After the diagnosis, they are expected to process large amounts of information in a short period of time and make quick treatment decisions/give their consent to treatment plans,¹¹ which often contributes to uncertainty, stress, and anxiety.⁴⁵ In the case of healthy siblings, parents may find it difficult to meet their needs, often leading to neglect.⁴⁶

As a result, *siblings* often feel jealous of the sick child.⁴⁶ They can feel rejected, lonely, isolated, and frustrated.⁴⁷ However, they also experience fear, guilt, and anger because of their sibling's disease.⁴⁷ The time during treatment can lead to a decreased quality of life and poorer school performance in siblings.⁴⁸

Even though *grandparents* play a central role in most families, especially when a child is chronically ill or disabled,⁴⁹ little research has been done on their psychosocial experiences in the context of childhood cancer. A recent systematic review on grandparents' experiences with childhood cancer identified only 12 studies conducted on the topic in the last decade.⁵⁰ The summary of these initial studies revealed that grandparents experienced a 'whirlwind of emotions' (e.g., helplessness, fear,

uncertainty, suffering) and a ‘double-whammy effect’ (i.e., witnessing two generations – their children and grandchildren – suffer).⁵⁰ In addition, grandparents reported providing a lot of support to the child’s family, but also challenges with finding their role in the family.⁵⁰ It is important to note that only one of the included studies was from Europe, and this study focused on bereaved grandparents.⁵¹

RESEARCH GAP 1:

Despite the recognized importance of grandparents’ psychosocial experiences in families with chronically ill or disabled children, there remains a significant gap in childhood cancer research, as evidenced by the limited number of existing studies. The lack of European evidence, especially during the time of active treatment, is particularly striking.

2.4. The long-term psychosocial impact of cancer and its treatment

Immediately after completing treatment, *survivors* may experience ambiguous feelings. Their emotions can range from relief and joy to feelings of isolation and the challenge of redefining ‘normal life’.⁵² Returning to school after treatment can provide a sense of normalcy for many, but can also elicit nervousness, decreased self-confidence, or feelings of being different from others.⁵² Again, survivors’ experiences are highly dependent on the age group they belong to (Figure 1), as cognitive factors (e.g., understanding of illness, autobiographical memory) and social factors (e.g., relationships with parents or peers) are highly age-dependent.²⁹

Over time, the negative feelings appear to decrease: Many adult survivors of childhood cancer perceive little impact of their former disease on functional aspects of adulthood, such as caregiving, finances, exercise, social-emotional relationships, and religion.⁵³ Yet, critical subgroups might experience psychosocial late effects.²⁷ As a group, they are at increased risk for depression and mood disorders, anxiety, psychological distress, post-traumatic stress, behavioral problems, and suicidal ideation.⁵⁴ Even without the experience of cancer, childhood, adolescence, and young adulthood are challenging periods of life, marked by enormous developmental tasks, such as graduating from high

school, choosing a career, or finding a partner.^{11,55} Not surprisingly, these developmental transitions present additional challenges for childhood cancer survivors.⁵⁵

In addition to these 'generic' psychosocial challenges, survivors may face specific psychosocial late effects resulting from their cancer experience and/or physical late effects. A prominent concern of childhood cancer survivors is *fear of cancer recurrence*, which is the worry/concern that the cancer will return or progress.⁵⁶ Fear of cancer recurrence is highly prevalent among survivors and is related to other health concerns⁵⁶ and elevated with somatic symptoms, such as pain.⁵⁷ Furthermore, many childhood cancer survivors face cancer-related *fatigue*, a distressing, persistent sense of physical, emotional, or cognitive exhaustion, even long after treatment has ended.²⁷

One of the most difficult challenges childhood cancer survivors face is an increased risk of infertility (failure to achieve a successful pregnancy after at least one year of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse⁵⁸) due to the aforementioned aggressive treatments and their impact on the reproductive system.⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ Fertility is deeply connected to one's sense of identity, intimate relationships, and aspirations for the future,⁶² which is why (potential) infertility is devastating for those who want to have children in the future. Although a high proportion of survivors do not know their fertility status,⁶³ many are concerned about their fertility. *Fertility-related concerns*, also known as reproductive concerns, can be related to fertility potential, emotional and practical barriers to achieving pregnancy, one's own physical health affecting the ability to parent, a possible negative impact of cancer on the health of one's children, and disclosing possible infertility to a partner.⁶⁴ Because these concerns can have a significant negative impact on the psychosocial well-being of survivors, it is important to assess them thoroughly. Currently, the available literature on fertility-related concerns predominantly consists of qualitative studies.⁶⁵⁻⁷⁶

RESEARCH GAP 2:

While qualitative research provides rich insights into survivors' lived experiences surrounding fertility-related concerns, there remains a gap in quantitative studies. Quantitative studies are needed to complement qualitative content by providing data on the prevalence and associated factors of fertility-related concerns in larger samples. In addition, quantitative data can help validate qualitative findings, thereby strengthening the evidence base for informed decision-making in clinical practice and policy development.

Although *family members* seem to have fewer psychosocial late effects, their post-treatment journey is marked by mixed emotions and ongoing challenges. After the completion of treatment, *parents* describe mixed feelings as 'the end of treatment is not the end' for many.⁷⁷ Even though they experience relief and joy,⁷⁸ they might continue to experience negative emotions, such as fear of cancer recurrence, or a lack of support in their uncertainties.⁷⁷ Luckily, these negative feelings seem to decrease over time.⁷⁸ In the long term, mean scores for general psychological distress, coping, and family functioning appear to be in the normal range for parent populations.⁷⁹

Similarly, *siblings* and *grandparents* of childhood cancer survivors appear to be psychologically healthy.^{80,81} However, as with survivors themselves, critical subgroups might continue to experience psychosocial problems, even long into survivorship.^{79,80}

2.5. Psychosocial care for patients and their families during treatment and beyond

Despite the large body of literature documenting the psychosocial challenges of childhood cancer patients and their families during treatment and beyond, there have long been no uniform standards to address them,⁸² as most guidelines focus on physical late effects.⁸³ Therefore, the Psychosocial Standards of Care Project for Childhood Cancer (PSCPCC) group and an interdisciplinary group of experts and stakeholders developed 15 evidence- and consensus-based standards for pediatric psychosocial care.⁸² A simplified version of these standards is displayed in Table 1.

TABLE 1 Standards for the psychosocial care of children with cancer and their families

	Standard	Patient	Family	Time point	REC
1	Routine systematic assessments of psychosocial health care needs	✓	✓	N/S	Strong
2	Monitoring for neuropsychological deficits (if at risk)	✓		During and after treatment	Strong
3	Yearly psychosocial screening	✓		N/S	Strong
	Guidance on the need of life-long follow-up care	✓	✓	Repeated at each follow-up visit	
4	Access to psychosocial support and interventions	✓	✓	Throughout the cancer trajectory	Strong
5	Assessment of risk for financial hardship		✓	Time of diagnosis	Strong
	Referral for financial counseling (if at risk)		✓	N/S	
	Longitudinal reassessment		✓	Throughout the cancer trajectory	
6	Early and ongoing assessment of parent/caregiver mental health needs		✓	N/S	Strong
	Facilitated access to interventions		✓	N/S	
7	Psychoeducation, information, and guidance on acute and long-term effects	✓	✓	Throughout the cancer trajectory	Strong
8	Developmentally appropriate preparation and psychological intervention for invasive medical procedures	✓		N/S	Strong
9	Opportunities for social interaction	✓		During cancer treatment and into survivorship	Strong
10	Psychosocial supportive services for siblings		✓	N/S	Strong
11	School reentry support for school-age patients	✓		N/S	Strong
12	Routine assessment of adherence	N/S	N/S	Throughout treatment	Strong
13	Introducing palliative care concepts regardless of disease status	✓	✓		Strong
	End of life and bereavement care (if indicated)	(✓)	✓	End of life and beyond	
14	Assessment of family needs after a child's death		✓	After the child's death	Strong
15	Open, respectful communication and collaboration among providers, patients, and families	N/A	N/A	N/S	Strong
	Involvement of pediatric psychosocial providers as integral team members	N/A	N/A	N/S	Strong
	Specialized training of pediatric psychosocial providers	N/A	N/A	N/S	Low

Note: adapted from Wiener et al., 2015.⁸²

Abbreviations: N/A = not applicable; N/S = not specified; REC = recommendation.

These standards have a strong emphasis on *routine screening* and *assessment* to identify patients/survivors and families at risk for specific psychosocial problems (Standard 1,2,3,5,6,12,14). The Pediatric Psychosocial Preventative Health Model⁸⁴ provides a conceptual model to guide this process (Figure 3).

The model suggests that, in principle, all families should have access to support, but that support should be targeted to those who need it most. To identify these families, all should receive psychoeducation and be screened for risk indicators. Those with elevated distress scores should be monitored and receive interventions for specific symptoms as appropriate, and individuals with severe, escalating, or persistent distress should receive intensive specialized treatment from mental health professionals.⁸⁴

FIGURE 3 From universal screening to specialized treatment

Note: adapted from the Pediatric Psychosocial Preventative Health Model; Kazak, 2006.⁸⁴

Screening is usually conducted with brief standardized measures that provide an initial indication of the psychosocial risk.¹¹ Unfortunately, there is little practical guidance on how to effectively conduct screening for mental health problems in the context of childhood cancer. Although healthcare providers acknowledge many benefits of psychosocial risk screening, they report practical barriers to implementation.⁸⁵ Brief screening during survivorship is especially important because healthcare

professionals see patients less frequently than during treatment, leaving less time to discuss psychosocial challenges.

RESEARCH GAP 3:

While the benefits of psychosocial risk screening in childhood cancer survivorship care are recognized, and standards for psychosocial care emphasize screening, there is a notable lack of practical guidance on effective screening practices. Healthcare providers face practical barriers to implementing psychosocial screening, and a synthesis of practical information is needed.

A positive screening should be followed by a more *comprehensive clinical assessment* to further evaluate psychosocial risk.¹¹ In addition to targeted assessments of specific mental health domains such as anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress, or quality of life, clinical assessment may include medical history, psychiatric history, patient functioning, sibling functioning, caregiver functioning, family functioning, social and family support, coping skills, cultural factors, and perceived family strengths.¹¹

If the clinical assessment confirms the screening result, *psychosocial interventions and therapies* are likely appropriate. There are many different types of interventions and therapies that can be used for patients/survivors and families. These include cognitive behavioral therapy, play therapy, social skills training, narrative therapy, bibliotherapy, and more.¹¹

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the aforementioned research gaps, I aimed to answer the following research questions:

RESEARCH QUESTION 1:

What are the psychosocial experiences of grandparents during the acute phase of their grandchild's cancer treatment?

RESEARCH QUESTION 2:

How prevalent are fertility-related concerns among long-term survivors of childhood cancer and what factors are associated with these concerns?

RESEARCH QUESTION 3:

What practical information is relevant to mental health screening in childhood cancer survivorship?

4. METHODS

4.1. Semi-structured interviews

Qualitative research aims to gain a deeper understanding of a given phenomenon.⁸⁶ It should address a socially relevant problem, answer an open question, use an appropriate qualitative method to answer this question, and present the results in a systematized and generalized form so that types and theories can be developed.⁸⁷ Qualitative research is particularly suited to topics that have received little attention as it is primarily concerned with describing and understanding a phenomenon.⁸⁸ As there was only limited evidence on the psychosocial experiences of grandparents during the cancer treatment of their grandchild, I wanted to follow an explorative, and thus qualitative, approach to answer *Research Question 1*.

Semi-structured interviews, a method in qualitative research, allow for focus on core topics,⁸⁹ while still being flexible to new subjects that might emerge during the interviews.⁹⁰ As this paper was part of a larger project (GROKids⁹¹) that aimed to explore how grandparents are affected by their grandchild's cancer diagnosis, it was important to align the interview guide to the core topics of the

project (experiences, help and support, health and well-being, daily life and employment, relationships, advice to other grandparents, positive outcomes). While all these topics were covered in the interview guide, my analysis focused on the psychosocial experiences of grandparents, as this was my research question.

*Qualitative content analysis*⁹² was conducted using an inductive-deductive categorization approach, integrating deductive categories from the initial study results and research objectives of the GROKids-project with emergent data-driven categories. *Consensus coding*⁹³ was achieved through systematic, independent coding, discussion, and refinement, with the final coding scheme being reviewed and validated by two research.

4.2. Cohort studies

Quantitative methods are appropriate whenever researchers want to obtain generalizable data that is conducted in an objective way.⁹⁴ Cohort studies are observational studies in which subjects are selected on the basis of a defining characteristic and followed over time to determine outcomes, such as the development of a disease, with the aim of establishing associations between characteristics and outcomes.⁹⁵ Hospital-based, national, and international cohorts of childhood cancer survivors provide an excellent opportunity to study treatment-related late effects.⁹⁶

Considering that *Research question 2* aimed to determine the prevalence of fertility-related concerns among long-term survivors of childhood cancer and the factors associated with these concerns, a cohort study was an optimal way to address this question. As part of an international research semester in Calgary, Canada, I was able to use data from a single-center cohort of childhood cancer survivors in Alberta, Canada.

To assess the prevalence of fertility-related concerns, I used basic descriptive statistics and Fisher's exact/ χ^2 - and t-tests to assess associated factors. Because this cohort study allowed for longitudinal analyses, I was also able to describe how survivors reported fertility-related concerns over time and determine whether there were associated factors using Fisher's exact/ χ^2 - and t-tests.

4.3. Systematic literature reviews

Systematic literature reviews are syntheses of evidence that follow a rigorously structured process.⁹⁷ They aim to identify international evidence relevant to a specific research question and are usually conducted by groups of researchers.⁹⁷ In many health areas, there are many studies on the same topic, which is why it is helpful to systematically synthesize their results into a single whole.⁹⁸

Given the large amount of evidence already available on screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivors, the aim was not to add to the evidence with an original study, but rather to draw new conclusions from the existing evidence. For this reason, a systematic review was the method of choice to answer *Research Question 3*.

In order to improve the methodological quality of the systematic review, it was registered in the Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), an international database dedicated to tracking systematic reviews in health and social care. This registration not only increases transparency but also guards against duplication and bias in the research process. Additionally, the review was based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Statement.⁹⁹ This statement helps to make the review objectives, methods, and results transparent by providing detailed reporting recommendations.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Exploring grandparents' psychosocial responses to childhood cancer:

A qualitative study

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Objective: A childhood cancer diagnosis is a traumatic experience for patients and their families. However, little is known about the effect on grandparents. We aimed to investigate the negative psychosocial impact, coping strategies, and positive outcomes of grandparents of childhood cancer patients in Switzerland.

Methods: We collected data using a semi-structured interview guide and applied qualitative content analysis.

Results: We conducted 20 interviews with 23 grandparents (57% female; mean age = 66.9 years; SD = 6.4; range = 57.0–82.4) of 13 affected children (69% female; mean age = 7.5 years; SD = 6.1; range = 1.0–18.9) between January 2022 and April 2023. The mean time since diagnosis was 1.0 years (SD = 0.5; range = 0.4–1.9). Grandparents were in shock and experienced strong feelings of fear and helplessness. They were particularly afraid of a relapse or late effects. The worst part for most was seeing their grandchild suffer. Many stated that their fear was always present which could lead to tension and sleep problems. To cope with these negative experiences, the grandparents used internal and external strategies, such as accepting the illness or talking to their spouse and friends. Some grandparents also reported positive outcomes, such as getting emotionally closer to family members and appreciating things that had previously been taken for granted.

Conclusions: Grandparents suffer greatly when their grandchild is diagnosed with cancer. Encouragingly, most grandparents also reported coping strategies and positive outcomes despite the challenges. Promoting coping strategies and providing appropriate resources could reduce the psychological burden of grandparents and strengthen the whole family system.

Keywords: cancer, child, family, grandparents, humans, oncology, positive psychology, psychological adaptation, psychological stress, Switzerland

5.2. Fertility-related concerns in long-term survivors of childhood cancer: a Canadian cohort study

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Purpose: To assess the prevalence of fertility-related concerns and identify associated factors among survivors of childhood cancer.

Methods: Self-report data were collected with the Long-Term Survivor Questionnaire at the Alberta Children's Hospital's Long-Term Survivor Clinic (LTSC) before or during regular follow-up appointments. Eligible participants were diagnosed with cancer before the age of 21 years, ≥ 2 years off therapy, and ≥ 13 years old at study inclusion. Data were collected between January 2021 and September 2023. We cross-sectionally analyzed fertility-related concerns for the whole sample and longitudinally for a sub-sample that completed three questionnaires during the study period.

Results: The sample consisted of $N=311$ survivors of childhood cancer (49.2% female; mean age at study=22.7 years, range=13.9-42.1; mean time since diagnosis=14.5 years, range=2.7-38.4), of whom 21.2% reported fertility-related concerns. Survivors with additional health concerns and those who were sexually active were more likely to report fertility-related concerns, whereas lymphoma survivors were least likely to report concerns. In the subsample who completed three questionnaires ($n=80$), 30% reported concerns at least once, whereas 9% expressed persistent concerns.

Conclusions: Fertility-related concerns are highly prevalent among young survivors of childhood cancer and warrant attention by healthcare providers throughout follow-up care.

Implications for Cancer Survivors: Services to systematically address fertility-related concerns in long-term follow-up are urgently needed. These services should provide a space to discuss concerns, provide education, and initiate fertility consultations, if desired.

Keywords: childhood cancer; survivorship; long-term outcomes; fertility-related concerns; reproductive health

5.3. Screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship: a systematic review

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Many survivors of childhood cancer suffer from psychological late effects. Therefore, regular psychological screening is strongly advised. Experts recommend screening for mental disorders and symptoms for all survivors at every follow-up visit, regardless of age. However, there is little practical guidance on screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship care. The aims of this systematic review were to (a) collect comprehensive information on available screening tools, (b) determine which health care professionals performed the screening, and (c) identify practical considerations regarding the timing of screening. The databases PubMed, PsycINFO, and CINAHL were systematically searched for peer-reviewed publications concerning childhood cancer, mental health problems, survivorship, and screening published between January 1990 and January 2023. The search yielded 2268 potentially relevant articles, of which 32 were included in the narrative synthesis. We found that (a) many suitable screening tools are available for the target population, of which the Distress Thermometer, Brief Symptom Inventory-18, Symptom Checklist-90, and Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory were the most commonly used in all studies; (b) professionals of different disciplines were involved in screening, and examples include clinical nurse specialists and psychologists; and (c) early onset, regular, and long-term screening are recommended if resources are available. In conclusion, selecting a screening tool in a clinical setting depends on various factors such as time and cost. However, many brief screening tools can be easily implemented without a large investment of resources. Furthermore, professionals from various disciplines can perform the screening. If they have no background in psychology, training is recommended to give them confidence in dealing with mental health issues. In conclusion, consistent and regular mental health screening is crucial for childhood cancer survivors, and we believe that the benefits outweigh the costs.

Keywords: cancer survivorship, screening, depression, anxiety, implementation

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Summary of key findings

*The first study*¹⁰⁰ explored the psychosocial experiences of grandparents during the acute phase of their grandchild's cancer treatment and found that they had decreased emotional well-being expressed in a variety of emotions, including shock, disbelief, fear, worry, overwhelm, suffering, uncertainty, or anger. Grandparents also described strained relationships, such as with their spouse or the child's parents, or feelings of exclusion due to the hospital's Corona Virus Disease of 2019 (COVID-19) policies. In addition, this study provided insights into their unique role as grandparents, for example, the fact that most had previous experience with cancer due to their advanced age. However, grandparents used internal and external coping strategies as well as faith and spirituality to cope with the situation. Internal coping strategies included aspects such as illness acceptance, self-care, distraction, or information seeking. External resources included emotional support from loved ones or professional help. Most grandparents even reported positive outcomes such as getting closer to family members, gratitude and appreciation, admiration for their family, or personal growth, demonstrating the potential for positive family outcomes amidst adversity.

The second study highlighted the prevalence of fertility-related concerns among long-term survivors of childhood cancer. At the first measurement point, about one-fifth of participants expressed fertility-related concerns, and over time, this number increased to nearly one-third, with 9.0% experiencing persistent fertility concerns. Several factors were found to be associated with fertility-related concerns. Survivors who were concerned about other health problems and those who were sexually active were significantly more likely to report fertility-related concerns. In addition, lymphoma survivors were less likely to express concerns compared to solid tumor survivors. In the longitudinal analysis, older age at diagnosis and having undergone surgery were factors significantly associated with fertility-related concerns. Fertility-related concerns are thus highly prevalent and persistent among young survivors of childhood cancer and warrant attention by healthcare providers throughout follow-up care.

*The third study*¹⁰¹ was a systematic literature review conducted to summarize important information to guide the implementation of screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship. Based on 32 studies, this review provided an overview of 42 screening tools for depression and mood disorders, anxiety, psychological distress, post-traumatic stress, behavioral problems, suicidality, and comprehensive psychological assessments. Furthermore, there were tools that included psychological problems but had a different overall focus. The most frequently used tools in all domains were the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (Peds-QL), the Distress Thermometer (DT), the Symptom Checklist-90 (SCL-90), and the Brief Symptom Inventory-18 (BSI-18). Various professionals (e.g., psychologists, nurses) were able to conduct screening, but there appears to be an advantage in having a positive relationship with the survivor and feeling comfortable in addressing mental health issues. Targeted training could improve the preparedness of health professionals in this regard. Concerning the timing of mental health screening, there was a broad consensus that screening should be performed on a regular basis and can be well integrated into follow-up appointments.

Collectively, these findings expand our understanding of the psychosocial context of childhood cancer and provide valuable insights into how to better understand and support patients and their families throughout the whole cancer continuum.

6.2. Towards family-centered care in childhood cancer

This dissertation's *first study* expands our understanding of family dynamics in childhood cancer by exploring the experiences of grandparents during the acute phase of treatment. It shed light on the often-neglected role of grandparents and offered insight into their unique experiences. This broader perspective underscores the importance of including the entire family in both psychosocial oncology research and practice, moving beyond the traditional focus on the immediate nuclear family to include a broader network of caregivers and affected family members.

Family-centered care is a health-care delivery approach that advocates the support and active involvement of families.¹⁰² In the context of childhood cancer, it can be defined as follows:

Family-centered care in childhood cancer is a contextual, customized approach to the care of families who have a child diagnosed with cancer that involves interdisciplinary as well as family collaboration, communication that addresses family information needs and fosters trust, and that acknowledges the ripple effect of the diagnosis on functioning of the family as a system as well as individual members (Figure 1).

(Wilson, 2023, p.116)¹⁰³

FIGURE 4 Schematic representation of family-centered care in childhood cancer

Note: Adapted from Wilson (2023)¹⁰³

Integrating family-centered care principles into childhood cancer care is essential for affected families and consistent with the Standards for the Psychosocial Care of Children with Cancer and their Families (refer to chapter 2.5).⁸² While little has previously been known about the need to include grandparents in family-centered childhood cancer care,¹⁰⁴ our study suggests that they should be considered an integral part of the family,¹⁰⁰ especially during the acute phase of treatment when

emotional distress is heightened, and typical family roles and routines are disrupted (refer to chapter 2.3).

Although this field of research is still very young and limited information is available on how to effectively involve grandparents in childhood cancer care, a recent study has proposed a clinical assessment tool for grandparents.¹⁰⁵ This qualitative tool includes questions such as “How would you characterize your relationship with your grandchild?”, “What kind of things do you do for your family?”, “What behaviors have you had that make you proud of your role as grandmother/grandfather?”, or “If you were to praise three people who have been very supportive and important throughout this period, who would they be and what would you say to them?”.¹⁰⁵ Recognizing and integrating the role of grandparents, along with other family members, enables healthcare providers to provide comprehensive support, address multiple family needs, and improve treatment outcomes and family well-being (Figure 4).^{105,106}

However, because family dynamics can also be a source of conflict,¹⁰⁶ it is critical for providers to offer collaborative, communicative, and customized care, as every family is unique (Figure 4).¹⁰³

While strategies for engaging grandparents are still evolving, the development of tailored clinical assessment tools holds promise for improving overall family well-being. Ultimately, by recognizing and supporting the diverse needs of *all* family members, healthcare providers can make a significant contribution to improving overall family functioning and resilience in the face of childhood cancer to the ultimate benefit of the affected child.³⁹

However, it is important to emphasize that support does not have to come solely from the healthcare system; providers can also facilitate coping by providing input or referring to existing resources. For instance, studies with parents have shown that adaptive coping strategies often included support from extended family members, community members (e.g., friends, neighbors, church), and the workplace (e.g., flexible schedules),^{107,108} in addition to support from the healthcare team itself. Our findings suggest that the same is true for grandparents. However, if they were included in screening and assessment practices, it would be possible to identify the most vulnerable grandparents and potentially help them despite limited system resources.

6.3. Towards a comprehensive and lifelong approach to psychosocial care

The identification of fertility-related concerns among long-term survivors of childhood cancer in the *second study* of this dissertation is an important consideration for survivorship care. By acknowledging and addressing these concerns, healthcare providers can offer comprehensive support to survivors as they navigate the challenges of life beyond cancer. This recognition underscores the importance of a lifelong approach to childhood cancer care, in which attention to psychosocial well-being extends well beyond the end of treatment. It emphasizes the need for ongoing monitoring and intervention to promote holistic well-being and quality of life in survivors.

Building on this, the integration of mental health screening into survivorship care represents a significant paradigm shift in the provision of support. By highlighting available screening tools, timing considerations, and professionals who can conduct screening, the *third paper* of this dissertation offers practical strategies for improving psychosocial care. This proactive approach to mental healthcare not only facilitates early identification and intervention, but also fosters a culture of openness and support for psychosocial well-being in the cancer care setting.

Ideally, these two components of survivorship care should be offered together: While it is important to offer general screening for mental health problems,⁵⁴ it would be desirable to include cancer-specific concerns, such as fertility-related concerns, fatigue, or fear of cancer recurrence. However, as screening is usually conducted with brief measures,¹¹ subsequent clinical assessments might be necessary for such a comprehensive approach to psychosocial follow-up care.

Engagement in long-term survivorship care has demonstrated numerous benefits for survivors, such as increased cancer-related knowledge, or accurately reporting late effects.¹⁰⁹ Even those who attend a survivor clinic are in need of continued education on cancer treatments, recommended follow-up practices and the importance of survivorship care,¹¹⁰ underscoring the critical importance of lifelong survivorship care for survivors. Factors such as younger age at diagnosis, parental involvement in decision-making, and motivation are positively associated with follow-up participation.¹¹¹

Importantly, comfort discussing health concerns with providers is also significantly associated with

participation,¹¹¹ underscoring the importance of translating our findings from study 2 into follow-up care. However, there are several barriers to regular attendance, resulting in a loss to follow-up. These include lack of awareness or interest,¹¹⁰ difficulties in transitioning from pediatric to adult-focused services,¹¹² as well as demographic (e.g., low socioeconomic status), medical, or logistical factors (e.g., work/school conflicts).¹¹³

Despite participation in survivorship programs, psychosocial care may not be guaranteed due to challenges in pediatric psychosocial follow-up.¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶ Many healthcare professionals lack comprehensive training in addressing psychosocial aspects, particularly when it comes to sensitive topics such as fertility and sexuality, resulting in unmet needs.^{114,117} A previous study from Switzerland found that while the majority of healthcare professionals reported that assessment of psychological distress was not standard in their follow-up program, about half believed that it was adequately assessed,¹¹⁸ highlighting the potential ignorance of providers about the need for systematic psychosocial follow-up. In addition, (minor) survivors and their parents may have conflicting views (e.g., about fertility preservation), with clinicians caught in the middle.^{66,73,114} Furthermore, communication with childhood cancer survivors is challenging due to different developmental stages (Figure 1), making it difficult for healthcare professionals to address appropriately.¹¹⁴ Although childhood cancer is traditionally diagnosed up to the age of 19, the overlap with adolescent and young adult (AYA) cancers during the teenage years has led to calls to consider the teen years as part of AYA cancers.¹¹⁹ Finally, childhood cancer survivors may have a tendency to deny difficulties,¹²⁰ which can make it difficult to discuss them altogether.

6.4. Strengths and limitations

While this dissertation offers valuable insights into various facets of psychosocial childhood cancer research and care, it is not without limitations. Apart from the limitations outlined in each study individually (Study 1: subjective interpretation by researchers and participants, difficulty distinguishing cancer journey from general experience, potential recruitment bias, variability in timing of interviews after diagnosis, potential influence of social desirability on self-reported outcomes; Study 2: broadness of the question “Do you have any fertility-related concerns?”, lack of information on survivors’ fertility

status and their knowledge about it, inability to include potentially relevant factors due to small subgroups, limited number of participants completing multiple questionnaires, need for a more comprehensive approach to assessing fertility-related concerns, need to include provider perspectives and survivors' explicit needs; Study 3: limited external validity due to inclusion of studies primarily conducted in high-income countries, caution required in interpreting statements about implementation as most included studies were conducted for research purposes, results may not fully apply to real-world settings, limited evidence available for review questions 2 and 3), there were several overarching limitations. As noted in the preface, all studies in this dissertation were conducted in or related to high-SDI settings, which limits their generalizability to a global context. It is important to acknowledge that this dissertation does by far not cover all relevant aspects of psychosocial research and care in childhood cancer, but only focuses on specific aspects. Since a dissertation is limited to a certain time period, an additional limitation is that the research gaps identified in the individual studies could not be further explored.

On a positive note, however, this also means that this dissertation provides numerous important impulses for future research while at the same time adding important new findings to the existing body of literature. Besides the strengths of each individual study (Study 1: In-depth exploration of grandparents' experiences, including both positive and negative impacts, incorporating all language regions in Switzerland, sample size exceeding previous qualitative research on the topic, significant participation of grandfathers; Study 2: first study to examine fertility-related concerns in Alberta, Canada, prevalence and associated factors assessed cross-sectionally and over time, high proportion of male survivors, helps inform future research and further development of the survivorship program; Study 3: rigorous methodology, followed PRISMA guidelines, searched more than 30 years of literature, broad and comprehensive overview, valuable data for professionals and scholars in the field), there are some overarching strengths. All studies underlying this dissertation were conducted by multiple and interdisciplinary researchers, enhancing the robustness and credibility of their findings. In addition, each study had a unique study design that allowed for the assessment of psychosocial issues from different perspectives. Furthermore, the studies represent diverse

geographical locations and demographic characteristics, contributing to the richness and applicability of the research findings to varied (high-SDI) contexts.

6.5. Implications for psychosocial oncology research

The cumulative impact of all three studies within this dissertation has undoubtedly contributed significant insights to the existing body of literature. However, these studies have also revealed new research gaps that require further exploration. In addition to the research gaps identified in the individual studies (Study 1: explore the exact nature of support needed and provided by grandparents, associations between negative experiences, coping strategies, and positive outcomes, information and support needs; Study 2: take a more comprehensive approach to assessing fertility-related concerns, include provider perspectives and survivor needs; Study 3: studies in a clinical setting, consider adaptive, electronic screening tools), the focus of the research inspired by this dissertation should be on clinical implication. Moving forward, research should provide a concrete link to real-world feasibility and applicability. By prioritizing this directive, researchers can effectively bridge the gap between theoretical insights and practical implementation, ultimately improving the actual quality of care and support provided to childhood cancer patients and their families.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Childhood cancer patients and their families face multiple psychosocial challenges that require attention in both the immediate and long-term contexts, underscoring the importance of a holistic approach to childhood cancer care beyond medical considerations.

This dissertation has made significant contributions to understanding and addressing these needs across the cancer continuum. It highlights the importance of considering grandparents in the childhood cancer context and suggests including them in family-centered childhood cancer care, especially in the acute phase of treatment. Furthermore, it advocates for a holistic and lifelong approach to psychosocial support, especially for survivors themselves, including the exploration of fertility-related concerns and early identification of general mental health problems through systematic screening.

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Appendix A – CV

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name **Pauline Holmer**
Address Dornacherstrasse 4, 6003 Lucerne, Switzerland
Date and place of birth 29.01.1997, Munich, Germany
ORCID 0000-0002-2734-5207

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

07 · 2021 - ongoing **Research assistant** (GROKids project)
University of Lucerne (CH)
Acute and long-term impacts of a child's cancer diagnosis on grandparents

EDUCATION

09 · 2023 - 02 · 2024 **Research semester abroad**
University of Calgary (CA)
Amsterdam University Medical Centers, Cancer Center Amsterdam (NL)

08 · 2021 - ongoing **PhD student** in Health Sciences
Psychosocial impact of childhood cancer
University of Lucerne (CH)

02 · 2019 - 06 · 2021 **MSc Psychology**, *in signi cum laude*
Specialization: clinical psychology and health psychology
University of Fribourg (CH)

10 · 2015 - 01 · 2019 **BSc Psychology**
University of Potsdam (DE)

07 · 2015 **High School Graduation**
Europäische Gesamtschule Insel Usedom (DE)

INTERNSHIPS

07 · 2020 – 11 · 2020 **Research Internship**
Institute for Family Research and Counseling, Fribourg (CH)

01 · 2020 – 02 · 2020 **Clinical Internship**
MEDIGREIF Inselklinik, Seebad Heringsdorf (DE)

GRANTS/AWARDS

2023/24 **Research Mobility Grant**
30,052 CHF

SCHOLARSHIPS

2015 - 2021 **Konrad Adenauer Foundation**
Interdisciplinary seminars across Europe, non-material support, financial sponsorship

MEMBERSHIPS

2022 – ongoing **Swiss Psychological Society**
(SPS SGP SSP; CH)

2022 – ongoing **Föderation der Schweizer Psychologinnen und Psychologen**
(Federation of Swiss Psychologists; FSP; CH)

2022 – ongoing **Schweizerische Vereinigung für Kinder- und Jugendpsychologie**
(Swiss Association for Child and Adolescent Psychology; SKJP; CH)

2022 – ongoing **PanCare**
(Pan-European Network for Care of Survivors after Childhood and Adolescent Cancer; NL)

PUBLICATIONS (submitted and published)

2024 – submitted to **Holmer, P.,** Henry, B., Duong, J., Lawal, O., Filder-Benaoudia, M.,
Reproductive Health Reynolds, K., Michel, G., Lehmann, V., Schulte, F.S.M., (2024). Fertility-related concerns among long-term childhood cancer survivors: a Canadian cohort study.

2024 – submitted to Russell, K.B., Roberts, A., Wright, H., Henry, B., Omobhude, F., **Holmer,**
Supportive Care in **P.,** Drummond, R., Verhesen, T., Forbes, C., Stokoe, M., Tomfohr-
Cancer Madsen, L., Schulte, F. (2024). Fear of cancer recurrence experienced by pediatric survivors of childhood cancer: A scoping review.

2024 **Holmer, P.,** Mühlebach, N., Ilic, A., Priboi, C., Roser, K., Raguindin, P.F., Tinner, E.M., Baechtold, R., Ansari, M., Diezi, M., Lemmel, E., Schilling, F.H., Farrag, A., Scheinemann, K., Michel, G., (2024). Exploring grandparents' psychosocial responses to childhood cancer: a qualitative study. *Psycho-Oncology*, 33(2), e6304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pon.6304>

2024 – submitted to Priboi, C., Ilic, A., **Holmer, P.,** Raguindin, P.F., Roser, K., Scheinemann, K., Tinner, E.M., Baechtold, R., Ansari, M., Diezi, M., Lemmel, E., Schilling, F., Michel, G. (2023). Psychological distress in grandparents whose grandchildren survived childhood cancer - Results from the GROkids project.

2023 Bolliger, C., **Holmer, P.,** Dehler, S., Roser, K., & Michel, G. (2023). Posttraumatic growth and illness perception in survivors of adolescent and

- young adult cancer. *Discover Oncology*, 14(1), 194.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12672-023-00810-3>
- 2023 **Holmer, P.**, Bolliger, C., Vokinger, A. K., Dyntar, D., & Michel, G. (2023). Screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship: a systematic review. *Journal of Psychosocial Oncology Research and Practice*, 5(3), 00.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/OR9.000000000000108>
- 2022 Priboi, C., Gantner, B., **Holmer, P.**, da Silva, L. N., Tinner, E. M., Roser, K., & Michel, G. (2022). Psychological outcomes and support in grandparents whose grandchildren suffer from a severe physical illness: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, e09365.
- 2020 Schöbi, B., **Holmer, P.**, Rapicault, A. & Schöbi, D. (2020). Bestrafungsverhalten von Eltern in der Schweiz. Eine wissenschaftliche Begleitung der Präventionskampagne “Starke Ideen – Es gibt immer eine Alternative zur Gewalt”. Bern: Kinderschutz Schweiz.

PUBLICATIONS (in preparation)

- Holmer, P.**, Ospelt, M., Michel, G., Lehmann, V., Schulte, F.S.M. Fertility-related concerns in childhood cancer survivors: a systematic review.
- Holmer, P.**, Michel, G., Lehmann, V. Self-esteem and its associations with body image, maturity, and satisfaction with life in young adult survivors of childhood cancer
- Tutelman, P.R., **Holmer, P.**, Reynolds, K., Fidler-Benaoudia, M., Lawal, O, Schulte, F.S.M. (2024). Patterns and predictors of suicidality in survivors of childhood cancer.
- Ospelt, M., **Holmer, P.**, Tinner, E. M., Mader, L., Hendriks, M., Michel, G., Kälin, S., Roser, K. Insurance, legal, and financial hardships of childhood and adolescent cancer survivors - a systematic review
- Heller, I., Bolliger, C., **Holmer, P.**, Schumacher Dimech A., Michel, G. The effects of sports and social support on social anxiety in young adults.
- Heller, I., Bolliger, C., **Holmer, P.**, Schladerer, S., Michel, G. The role of social skills training in the treatment of social anxiety: a systematic review.

PRESENTATIONS

- 2023 **Holmer, P.**, Muehlebach, N., Ilic, A., Priboi, C., Roser, K., Raguindin, P.F., Tinner, E.M., Baechtold, R., Ansari, M., Diezi, M., Lemmel, E.,

- Scheinemann, K., Michel, G. (2023). Exploring the psychological impact of a childhood cancer diagnosis on grandparents: negative outcomes, coping strategies, and positive outcomes: a qualitative study [poster presentation], 55th Congress of the International Society of Pediatric Oncology (SIOP), International Society of Pediatric Cancer (SIOP), Ottawa, Canada.
- 2023 **Holmer, P.** (2023). Childhood cancer: the role and needs of grandparents [lecture], Psycho-Oncology, University of Calgary, Canada.
- 2023 **Holmer, P.**, Bolliger, C., Vokinger, A.K., Dyntar, D., Michel, G. (2023). Screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship: A systematic review [poster presentation], IPOS World Congress, Milano, Italy.
- 2023 **Holmer, P.**, Bolliger, C., Vokinger, A.K., Dyntar, D., Michel, G. Screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship: A systematic review [oral presentation], Research Symposium Health Lucerne, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland.
- 2022 **Holmer, P.**, Bolliger, C., Vokinger, A.K., Dyntar, D., Michel, G. Screening for mental health problems in childhood cancer survivorship: A systematic review [poster presentation], 54th Congress of the International Society of Pediatric Oncology (SIOP), International Society of Pediatric Cancer (SIOP), Barcelona, Spain.